

Holzmühle Westerkamp

Wood flour and fibres

The producer of high-quality wood flour, wood fibres, wood granulate and lignocellulose provides a source material for high added value applications in the food and feed industry and for the manufacturing of a diverse set of biobased products.

Highlights of innovative features

- The company is working according to a strict product quality standard needed to supply their main market the food and feed industry with feed mixes and litter material.
- Applications also include the production of compostable or non-compostable biobased products such as wood plastic composites.
- Due to the high-quality of wood flours needed in the feed and food industry, the lignocellulose can also be used in high-end processes such as filtration of glucose, starch, oil and used fats.
- Used plant-based fats can be cleaned to produce biodiesel while the remaining filter cake can be used for heat or energy production.

Lignocellulose is the source material for various products and is made from wood milled to a homogenous material reaching from flour up to coarser particles. Holzmühle Westerkamp constantly develops new tailor-made products in close cooperation with their clients to satisfy their needs and explore new markets.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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